

Ecobreed: Evaluating wireworm (Coleoptera: Elateridae) control strategies in potato

Eva PRAPROTNIK¹, Primož ŽIGON¹, Špela MODIC¹, Peter DOLNIČAR², Jaka RAZINGER¹

¹ **Plant Protection Department, Agricultural Institute of Slovenia**, Ljubljana, Slovenia

² **Crop Science Department, Agricultural Institute of Slovenia**, Ljubljana, Slovenia

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Wireworms (Coleoptera: Elateridae) are one of the most important soil pests of potatoes.

They can be found in the soil where they feed on the underground parts of plants, such as the roots and tubers of potatoes. Damage from wireworms can include wilting, stunted growth, and even plant death.

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- Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF), particularly from the genus *Metarhizium* (Ascomycota: Hypocreales), have been shown to be a promising solution for wireworm control in potatoe
- Entomopathogenic fungi are primarily known for their ability to parasitize insects and kill or severely harm them

Spore development of entomopathogenic fungi on insects. (a) healthy wireworm; (b) wireworm infected with *Metarhizium*; (c) healthy Colorado potato beetle larva; (d) Colorado potato beetle larva infected with *Beauveria*.

Entomopathogens can also colonize the rhizosphere and plant tissues as endophytes and act as plant growth promoters. Photo: Chaudary et. al 2023

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- **Aim of the study:** test different formulations based on EPF *Metarhizium brunneum* and *Metarhizium robertsii*.

- **Attracap** - biological insecticide based on EPF *Metarhizium brunneum*
 - **full dose**
 - **half dose**
- seed potato tubers were soaked in the suspension of the six highly virulent *Metarhizium* isolates from the mycological collection of the Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (**potato + fungi**)
- (**potato + rice**) fungal formulation of six *Metarhizium* isolates multiplied on rice
- (**potato + fungi + rice**) a combination of the above-mentioned fungal treatments
- **Force** - chemical insecticide conventional control
- Untreated **control**

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Set-up

Buffer zone							
4	1	2	2	6	3	5	3
1	4	1	4	5	1	2	2
5	6	3	6	4	2	1	5
3	5	4	1	2	4	3	6
2	3	5	3	1	5	6	4
6	2	6	5	3	6	4	1
Buffer zone							

Location 1

Buffer zone					
4	1	2	2	6	3
1	4	1	4	5	1
5	6	3	6	4	2
3	5	4	1	2	4
2	3	5	3	1	5
6	2	6	5	3	6
Buffer zone					

Location 2

2020

Buffer zone							
4	1	2	2	6	3	5	3
1	4	1	4	5	1	2	2
5	6	3	6	4	2	1	5
3	5	4	1	2	4	3	6
2	3	5	3	1	5	6	4
6	2	6	5	3	6	4	1
Buffer zone							

Location 3

Buffer zone							
4	1	2	2	6	3	5	3
1	4	1	4	5	1	2	2
5	6	3	6	4	2	1	5
3	5	4	1	2	4	3	6
2	3	5	3	1	5	6	4
6	2	6	5	3	6	4	1
Buffer zone							

Location 4

2021

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LEGEND:

- A** Control
- B** Attracap half dose
- C** Attracap
- D** Potato + fungi
- E** Force
- F** Potato + fungi +rice
- G** Potato + rice

Clear difference of wireworm pressure between years

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Net tuber yield showed no significant differences between treatments

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CONCLUSIONS

- 🍷 Bioinsecticides based on entomopathogenic fungi were not so effective in reducing the number of tunnels per potato tuber, but were more efficient at reducing % of damaged tubers
- 🍷 efficacy of **fungi formulated on rice (potato + rice)** may be comparable to commercial bioinsecticides and chemical insecticides
 - 🍷 reducing % of damaged tubers for 42 %
- 🍷 Potato tubers soaked in fungal suspension showed to be the least effective in reducing wireworm damage

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Thank you for your attention

Consortium

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